

Oxidation of Hydrocarbons Part—I. Catalytic Oxidation of Liquid-Paraffin at 403°K*

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Air-oxidation of liquid-paraffin has been carried out at 403°K in the presence of a number of cobalt salts as catalysts over a period of 13 hrs. Acid values of the product samples drawn at regular interval of time have been determined. Effect of the nature and amount of the catalyst on the initiation period and rate of oxidation have also been studied. It is found that recycling of even 1% of the product into the fresh charge improves, considerably, the initiation period.

OXIDATION of hydrocarbons is of significant importance as the product could further be used in manufacturing detergents, synthetic fibres, rubbers, plastics and a number of high quality solvents. Emanuel¹ published a thematic collection of several investigations in the field of hydrocarbons-oxidation. The synthetic applications of these reactions are described by Augustine². For the mechanism of these reactions one can refer to the monographs of Stewart³ and Wiberg⁴. Ducknell⁵ reviewed, critically, the selective oxidation of C₂-to C₈-olefins and alkanes.

Earlier^{1,6-12} attempts have been made to study the liquid-phase oxidation of cyclohexane, n-decane, n-hexadecane, paraffin-wax and a number of aromatic hydrocarbons. In the above investigations the catalysts used were calcium- and magnesium-naphthenates, cobalt stearates, boric acid, KMnO₄, MnO₂, Cr₂O₃, etc.

However, for a deeper insight into the subject involving the study of kinetics and reaction mechanism of oxidation of hydrocarbons, a thorough experimentation is still needed. We have undertaken a systematic study of oxidation of hydrocarbons in the liquid phase. The present work deals with the oxidation of liquid-paraffin at 403°K using air as the oxidant in the presence of different salt-catalysts. The choice of using cobalt salts as catalysts in the present investigations is of special interest. Bivalent cobalt having unpaired electrons in its 3d orbitals is expected to exhibit the properties of weak radicals. Catalysts used are cobalt oxalate (I), cobalt bromide (II), cobalt oxide (III), cobalt naphthenate (IV), and calcium stearate (V). It was aimed to study the effect of nature and amount of catalyst on the initiation period and rate of oxidation of total hydrocarbons present in liquid-paraffin. Attempt has also been made to study the effect of recycling the oxidised product.

Experimental

Materials: Liquid-paraffin used was of IP grade. Its number-average molecular weight found by

depression in freezing point method (using benzene as solvent) is 321. Its boiling range and density were found to be 578-583°K and 0.8282 gm. cm⁻³ (at 303°K) respectively.

Cobalt oxalate (Thomas Tyrer), cobalt bromide (BDH, LR), cobalt oxide (Apex Chemicals), cobalt naphthenate (Chemilon Lab. Chem.) and calcium stearate (Atlas Lab. Chem.) were used as such.

Apparatus: The apparatus used for the oxidation of liquid-paraffin consists of a reaction cell made of 25 cm. long corning glass tube T of 5 cm. diameter (Fig. 1). Tube T is fitted with a head H by means

Fig. 1. Apparatus used for the oxidation of liquid-paraffin.

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of a taper joint (size B-34). A water condenser C is fitted over the side arm S by means of a standard joint (size B-24). An internal tube I of 0.8 cm. diameter fused through the top of head H terminates 1 cm. above the bottom of tube T.

Oil-thermostat BB consists of an iron container ($40 \times 40 \times 50 \text{ cm}^3$) properly insulated from outside to minimise heat losses. This was achieved by keeping the iron container inside a wooden box of slightly larger dimension and filling the gap with thick cardboards and wood-dust. For temperature control the thermostat was fitted (not shown in Fig. 1) with an electrically run stirrer, an immersion heating rod (1000 W), toluene regulator and a sunvic relay.

Procedure: 100 ml sample of liquid-paraffin was taken in the reaction cell. After the required amount of the catalyst had been added to the sample, the reaction cell was kept vertical in the oil-bath, temperature of which was maintained at 403°K ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The water condenser was then fitted in position. Air at the rate of 12.8 litres/min. was bubbled through the sample. 5 ml portion each of the product samples were withdrawn at an interval of 1-2 hours and their acid values were determined.

To determine acid values a known weight of the sample (about 2 gms) was taken in a titration flask. It was titrated against standard alcoholic KOH solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. However, the end point (colourless to pink) for samples collected after 11 hours of oxidation were not sharp.

Results and Discussion

In Fig. 2, plots of acid values versus time are given. In each case the concentration of the different catalysts used was 0.375% W/V. Using cobalt naphthenate as catalyst it is observed that the formation of carboxylic acid starts just after 1 hour. But in cobalt oxide or cobalt bromide-catalysed oxidation, carboxylic acids are formed only after three hours. The initiation period is prolonged even to 8 hours if cobalt oxalate is used as the catalyst. However, after the initiation period the rate of carboxylic acid formation is almost similar regardless of the nature of anion present in the cobalt salt. This is obvious from the slopes of the curves in Fig. 2. In case of cobalt bromide and cobalt naphthenate as catalysts, increase of carboxylic acids in the product ceases after 10-12 hours.

Acid values reached after 10 hours of oxidation using following catalysts are in the order: (II) > (IV) > (III) > (I) > (V) = without catalyst.

Effective catalytic action of Co^{+3} (Electronic configuration $.3s^2 3p^6 3d^7$) may be attributed to the presence of unpaired electrons in its 3d orbitals and hence its ability to exhibit radical properties. The magnitude and rate of carboxylic acids formed in calcium stearate catalysed reactions are almost similar as for the non-catalysed reaction (Fig. 2). The non-catalytic behavi-

our of calcium stearate may be due to the absence of unpaired electrons in Ca^{+2} (electronic configuration $.3s^2 3p^6$).

Fig. 2. Kinetics of carboxylic acids formation during oxidation of liquid-paraffin using different catalysts (each 0.375% W/V) at 403°K .

- cobalt oxide
- cobalt naphthenate
- △— cobalt bromide
- ▲— cobalt oxalate
- calcium stearate
- ×— without catalyst

Effect of recycling the oxidised product was also studied. The initiation period is noticeably reduced by recycling even very small amount (1% of the total charge) of the product. It is evident from the plots of the acid values in Fig. 3. In this case the sample recycled was pre-treated for oxidation for a period of 7 hours. The reason for the above decrease of initiation period may be that the recycled sample provides a stock of active intermediates like hydroperoxides¹⁰ which readily initiate and propagate the chain reactions with the hydrocarbons present in the fresh charge.

In Fig. 4, the effect of amount of catalyst (viz cobalt naphthenate) on the rate of carboxylic acid formation has been depicted. It is observed that at low concentrations of catalyst (upto 0.75% W/V) amount as well as rate of carboxylic acids formation enhance with the increase of catalyst-concentration. However, acid values corresponding to 3% W/V catalyst are lower than that for 0.75% W/V catalyst. It appears that there exists a limiting value of the catalyst concentration. A further increase in the amount of catalyst in excess of limiting value, instead of improving the rate of oxidation rather inhibits the reaction and hence decreases the yield of the carboxylic acids in the product.

Fig. 3. Effect of recycling the oxidized product on the carboxylic acids formation during oxidation of liquid-paraffin using cobalt bromide (0.375% W/V) as catalyst at 403°K.

—▲— only catalyst
—●— catalyst + 1% oxidized sample

Fig. 4. Effect of amount of catalyst (cobalt naphthenate) on the carboxylic acids formation during oxidation of liquid-paraffin at 403°K.

—■— 3.0% (W/V)
—▲— 0.750% (W/V)
—●— 0.375% (W/V)
—○— 0.000% (W/V)

Kamiya and Ingold¹¹ also observed the existence of critical catalyst-concentration during the study of oxidation of tetralin. Similar observations were made by Rouchard¹² during copper- or zinc-chelate catalysed oxidation of cumene. It is believed that at high concentrations cobalt may act as inhibitor of oxidation reactions terminating reaction chain.

No attempts were made to isolate the individual constituent compounds present in the product. However, a comparison of IR spectra of the pure liquid-paraffin and the product samples revealed that two additional absorption peaks—one at 1700 cm^{-1} and the other at 1170 cm^{-1} appeared in case of the product samples. The former frequency being characteristic of C=O (Stretching) of carboxylic acid group and the latter being characteristic of hydroperoxide (-C-O-O-H) group. This indicates that carboxylic acid, the ultimate product of these reactions, are formed via hydroperoxides as in intermediates.

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